

USING GAME METHODS AND TECHNIQUES IN ENGLISH LESSONS AS A WAY TO ENHANCE LEARNING

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Annotation

In the article, the author tries to determine the importance of using gaming techniques in learning English, as well as to analyze what effective gaming technologies exist

Key words

Game, game technology, teacher, foreign language lesson, classes, statistics, skill, perception.

The game is a huge bright, gentle, through which a life—giving stream of ideas and concepts about the world around the child flows into the spiritual world. Sufficient attention is paid to the formation of communication skills in the subject "English" in the educational environment. According to the educational standard in elementary grades, there are the following conversational skills (in a foreign language) that elementary school students should master: participation in a conversation, be able to request information, as well as be able to contact the teacher for clarification, respond to a partner's statement, showing their attitude, be able to participate in a dialogue, retell what they heard, so as it was understood — demonstrating an individual attitude to the topic.

In addition to dialogical speech, the younger student is supposed to lead a monologue speech: that is, to be able to tell about himself, his loved ones (family and friends), about intentions (with justification), to be able to express his attitude to the event, to tell about his life and culture of his country, his city, also knowing the basic data about the country of the language being studied. The above-described speech abilities can be developed in younger schoolchildren during their studies, while pedagogical experience shows that the traditional teaching methodology instills these skills for too long, therefore, it has research value to apply more innovative and consistent educational technologies to the psychology of students. Considering the game technique as a means of a communicative teaching method for developing the skill of speaking a foreign language, let us turn to the pedagogical experience of the West. A very important skill in order to master the skill of speaking is the ability to listen, and listen

carefully. The game method allows younger students to develop the ability to listen

The social realization of a student in English classes includes a communicative method, this side of mastering the speaking skill helps in the perception of intercultural and interpersonal communication.

The game is a spark that ignites a spark of inquisitiveness and curiosity. V. A. Sukhomlinsky The game is an integral part of any person's life. Everyone loved to play as a child. With the help of games and fantasy, we could be astronauts, pirates, princesses, or move around the world with the help of our imagination. The importance of the game is huge. Games contribute to the development of a sense of collectivism, imagination, initiative, determination, intelligence, and organization. In games, children's ideas about the surrounding life are clarified, their horizons are expanded; perception, thinking, attention, speech, and necessary movements are developing. Games create a cheerful and joyful mood for the child. For a reason, gaming is one of the important teaching methods, especially for younger students. It is at this age that there is a gradual change in the leading activity, the transition from playing to learning activities. At the same time, the game still retains its leading role.

Based on this feature, the game should become the basis for the development of students' learning skills. Different linguistic skills are developed in different games: listening, speaking, reading, writing [1]. The purpose of using game forms of learning in the classroom is to develop sustainable cognitive interest among students through a variety of game forms of learning.

To achieve this goal, you must complete the following tasks:

1) To promote the solid assimilation of educational material by students. 2) To develop students' creative thinking.

3) To promote the practical application of the skills and abilities acquired in the classroom.

4) To foster interest in a foreign language.

5) The use of game techniques helps to arouse children's desire to communicate in a foreign language, allows them to focus their attention on the main thing — mastering speech skills in the process of a natural communication situation during the game. To date, there is no single unambiguous classification of games, there are only conditional types of it. Let's consider M. F. Stronin's classification, which is most close to me. In his book Learning Games in English Lessons, he identifies two categories of games: The first category is grammatical,

lexical, phonetic and spelling games that contribute to the formation of language skills at the initial stage of learning.

The second category is creative games that contribute to the further development of speech skills and abilities, and allow you to show independence. Creative games include: 1) role-playing games; 2) story-role-playing games. Such games are aimed at using communication skills in certain situations. It is advisable to use such games with children of middle and high school age, when the preparatory speech stage has already been completed and students have the necessary speech skills [2].

An interesting grammatical game is "show action", the essence of the game is for one student to show actions, and the second to guess the necessary verbs that describe these actions. Another game worth paying attention to is the game "nonsense", the teacher says sentences at the right time, but specifically makes a mistake, the task of students is to find a mistake and correct it. The game "assemble me" consists in the fact that students receive pieces of sentences, their task is to assemble all the sentences correctly, placing all the parts in the correct order. Let's consider lexical games that are no less interesting than the previous games considered. They are aimed at helping children to master lexical material, expand their vocabulary, and use vocabulary in an appropriate situation.

The game "remember" consists in the fact that the teacher lays out 10 thematic cards with drawings in front of the students, all of them call the words in chorus. The teacher asks you to turn away or close your eyes and takes one card. Students should guess which card is missing by naming all 10 words in order. There are no cards left at the end, but the children name all the words in the correct order. The game "whisper" consists in the fact that the teacher whispers a word in the ear of the student, the other one and so on along the chain and the last student must name the word that he heard. Guessing game, the meaning of the game is that children are divided into teams, the teacher distributes pictures of rooms (bathroom, living room, bedroom), the task of children is to arrange words on objects in the picture. The game "Describe the picture", the essence of the game is that children, looking at the picture offered to them, try to describe it. Let's consider creative games that contribute to the further development of speech skills and abilities, and allow you to show independence. In these games, the imagination is trained, the child learns to see the unusual in the most ordinary things.

This is creativity, and thanks to it, free speech [3]. For example, making crosswords, drawing pictures and describing them, telling about your idol, about any actor / actress, creating greeting cards, telling about your favorite holiday and a lot of other creative tasks. The use of game technologies in English lessons can help the teacher to maintain and increase interest in the subject, however, it is important to remember that the game serves as a means of increasing the effectiveness of the lesson only when it is pedagogically and methodically directed. It is important to understand that when using games in their classes, it is necessary to know for sure whether children will be able to play this game, whether it will be understandable, interesting to them, whether it meets age requirements. The teacher should always remember such elementary requirements: it is unacceptable that not all students are involved in the game; it is necessary to create a friendly environment, observe a sense of tact, without devaluing anyone's abilities.

The world around us is full of various information. The task of the teacher is to attract the attention of students to themselves by applying modern technologies and methods. It is important to keep the learning process entertaining, diverse, new and different from other classes every time, to facilitate overcoming difficulties and difficulties in learning new material. The teacher's ability to move in the same direction with the progressive world is an opportunity for him not to lose the interest of students in the subject he teaches.

Speaking skills as a goal in teaching English include: Qualitative improvement of the level of English language proficiency; Game techniques quite simply present the subject of study, and allow younger students to naturally master spoken language itself, without participating in the constant "memorization" of grammatical rules; Game techniques more easily help elementary school students overcome the "language barrier" his shyness, speaking more freely and easier with native speakers [1].

The main purpose of teaching the development of speaking skills is to help students form (taking into account their real needs and interests) the skill of conversational participation, communication in new social situations for them. On the part of the teacher, a sufficient amount of effort is required so that students develop a speaking skill that is appropriate in terms of the quality of mastering foreign speech. Speaking can be expressed by type: monological and dialogical messages. In general, as already mentioned, listening and listening skills are important in speaking skills, which can be indicated as means of applying the communicative method in teaching.

In the educational process, in English classes, all skills must interact harmoniously: speaking, listening, writing, reading. Differentiation of these skills is allowed, at the same time, it is desirable to possess these skills at a high level, and try to master skills at an equal level of perception. It should be remembered that the speaking skill is very important, as it implies practical application.

Ferstov argues that it is important to explain not so much "grammar", that is, not the principle of "how", but to explain to the student "why exactly." It is very important to bring an understanding of "why this is so" for the ability to construct elementary phrases. The teacher should intelligently observe the zone of "entanglement" and make an appropriate understanding [2]. Students should know: according to what rules the dialogue is built, where to start the act of communication, how to build their speech so that the interlocutor understands your communicative intention. In an educational environment, the first stage is necessary to master the speaking skill.

The second and third stages in learning English are additional in language acquisition. At the second stage, it is important to determine what topics you want to talk about, after that you should choose the right preparatory material. Well-chosen material allows you to conduct an educational game in English lessons with minimal teacher participation. It will be useful to translate the text calmly and thoughtfully. That is, students need to be given some time to translate the text, albeit in a playful way. Ferstov believes that translation exercises help to maintain a "balance" in speaking a foreign language.

In learning English, it is required to use spoken language more often in the classroom, this is a modern communicative approach used in teaching. It is very useful to develop in elementary school students (regarding conversational reactions) the ability to instantly, upon mental request, pull out the necessary turns from memory, as well as in order to quickly understand what is being said, to carry out preparatory work on the translation skill (the second stage). It is recommended to focus on the speaking process in the English lesson during the development of spoken language. In the classroom, it is important to observe the atmosphere of the ability to listen to each other, if the student speaks, you should listen to him completely, not interrupt him, in order to maintain motivation for self-expression. The way a teacher expresses himself in an English lesson is important. In game technology, the teacher's sincere interest in his subject is also very important. The first person who speaks in class is the teacher himself. The teacher should be interested in understanding which game

is interesting to the student, since it is the teacher who directs students to arouse their real interest in the subject.

The game is recognized as an effective means of learning when traditional methods do not have the effect that is needed. Game technology is able to unlock the potential of perception of English classes, the game equally reveals the available opportunities for learning speaking skills for students, and it does not matter whether the student is weak or strong. Thanks to gaming technologies, the student is quite able to realize creative skills, demonstrate to himself and others his individual personality qualities, and even a small success in learning English becomes a very great help to support motivation in mastering a foreign language. Speaking skills are the most important in mastering the types of speech activity.

Considering the advantages of the game method as a communicative method in English classes, it is noted that the game method provides a tremendous incentive to learn a foreign language — this is a successful methodological technique. In a modern school, it is recommended to update the English language learning process, add active games to the lower grades, and also apply game technologies according to the psychological characteristics of students. Speaking skills are best formed if the classroom provides an atmosphere in which students can develop their personal qualities by working in a group or team. It is important to motivate children to work together, discover new things together, apply joint actions to solve tasks, and see new combinations. In modern society, it is important that each member of the team understands his own contribution, how it affects the success of the team. It is important for a teacher to think over the recruitment of teams in game educational processes, and for this it is necessary to take into account the individual attitude to each student and the nature of interpersonal relations in the educational team.

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